

TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP EFFECTS ON JOB PERFORMANCE: THE MEDIATING INFLUENCE OF AFFECTIVE COMMITMENT, JOB SATISFACTION, AND JOB INSECURITY IN MANUFACTURING ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract

The objective of this study was to examine the impact of transformational leadership on the performance of production employees in semiconductor manufacturing companies in Indonesia, with the mediating role of job satisfaction, job insecurity, and affective commitment. This perceptual research was conducted to achieve those objectives, using the Google Form online survey method from November 2023 to January 2024. This survey research method required respondents from the production employee population, with sampling focused on the operator and leader-level production employees. The results of the responses were 210 respondents. The data from this response was processed with a quantitative approach and analysed by structural equation modelling – partial least squares (PLS-SEM). SMART-PLS4 software was used to process the data. The findings of this study indicated that transformational leadership had a positive effect on the performance of production employees, both directly and indirectly. The role of mediating variables, including job satisfaction and commitment, in relation to performance showed a positive and significant effect. Conversely, the mediating variable of job insecurity had a negative effect. The effect size of the indirect effect of transformational leadership through job satisfaction and affective commitment variables was low. The effect size of the indirect influence of transformational leadership through job insecurity showed no effect on performance. To the best of the author's knowledge, research on the effect of transformational leadership on performance through the mediation of job insecurity was very rarely conducted with respondents of semiconductor production employees in Indonesia.

Keywords: Affective Commitment, Job Insecurity, Job Performance, Job Satisfaction, Transformational Leadership.

INTRODUCTION

Human resource management helps companies survive and grow in today's competitive business environment. Extensive competition from external and internal causes may force management to reduce staff to ensure the company's long-term existence (Alnahedh & Alrashdan, 2021), increase production efficiency, and promote sustainability. After layoffs, remaining employees generally perform poorly (Langster & Cutrer, 2021). Given these constraints, firms must continue to improve organizational performance for sustained growth. Transformational leadership is known to boost employee performance (Torlak & Kuzey, 2019), numerous studies showing its good impact on performance (Indradewa *et al.*, 2020; Jiatong *et al.*, 2022; S. Lee *et al.*, 2023; Manzoor *et al.*, 2019; Shao *et al.*, 2022; Sürücü *et al.*, 2022).

Manufacturing firms using transformational leadership need to be aware of the direct and indirect effects on performance through the mediating variables of job insecurity, job satisfaction, and affective commitment in order to achieve the expected performance (Eliyana *et al.*, 2019a; Gün *et al.*, 2021; Jiatong *et al.*, 2022; Kustiawan *et al.*, 2022; Shao *et al.*, 2022; Sürücü *et al.*, 2022). References to research results in

several countries with different business sectors might show the relationship between performance characteristics, work satisfaction, job instability, and affective commitment.

Performance of employees, especially first-level operators and production field managers—is essential for manufacturing companies to sustain continuous productivity and quality of produced goods. Particularly the semiconductor industry is critical to the expansion of the Indonesian and global economies. Thus, it is crucial to carry out this research in a well-known and sizable semiconductor manufacturing company in Indonesia, which is going through intense commercial competition right now. Two main gaps are identified by this study: first, the subject of study in Indonesian semiconductor manufacturing; and second, the respondents, survived employees. The second gap in the literature is that, although many investigations of the aforementioned variables, the mediating variable of job insecurity in the connection between transformational leadership and performance has hardly ever been used in earlier research. Drawing on the aforementioned justification, the purpose of this study was to investigate, in manufacturing organizations, the direct and indirect impacts of transformational leadership characteristics on performance via the mediating variables of affective commitment, job satisfaction, and job insecurity.

The two big multinational semiconductor manufacturing enterprises in Indonesia that are situated in the industrial district of Karawang are the subject of this study. Academic advantages from the study can advance our knowledge of the factors under investigation theoretically. After that, the companies as research and other businesses can apply the practical advantages of personnel resource management to sustain and enhance employee performance.

LITERATUR REVIEW

Transformational Leadership

Transformational leadership is the leader ability to make followers inspired to go above their self-interest in order to accomplish goals; followers are able to achieve and self-actualise because they are encouraged to face their own challenges (Bass & Bass, 2008). Transformational leadership can have a big influence on followers and motivate them to put the organization's interests first (Robbins & Judge, 2022). Achieving organizational goals requires the capacity to inspire members of the organization and mobilize human resources, which enhances and influences members' task performance and assisting behaviour (Antonakis & Day, 2020; Lai *et al.*, 2020). A proactive leader who promotes change, increases awareness among subordinates, and assists in the accomplishment of large goals is referred to as having transformational leadership (Busari *et al.*, 2020; Kaur Bagga *et al.*, 2023). One way to characterise transformational leadership is as a convincing process of interpersonal interaction and organizational mobilization. It can constantly raise awareness and trust among staff members to accomplish company objectives (Shao *et al.*, 2022).

Four aspects of transformational leadership include idealised influence, inspiring motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individualized consideration (Bass & Bass, 2008; Lyubykh *et al.*, 2022; Robbins & Judge, 2022; Shao *et al.*, 2022).

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a person's feelings about work and aspects of work (Spector, 2022), a favorable impression of a job that arises from assessing its features, such as the work itself, salary, advancement, management, and coworkers (Robbins & Judge, 2022). A general attitude of an employee toward his or her work, job satisfaction denotes a happy or good emotional state that arises from an assessment of the person's work or work experience (Kumar & Bhandarker, 2021). Generally speaking, one can see job happiness as a factor in both staff productivity and retention (Ali & Anwar, 2021). As the evolution of what people like and dislike about their work, job satisfaction is defined as how a person feels about their job and its many facets (Gün *et al.*, 2021). Luthans *et al.*, (2021) mentioned that job satisfaction is the intangible and only inferred emotional or cognitive response, job satisfaction also refers to how much people feel good or bad about their jobs.

The two primary groups into which Weiss *et al.* (1967) categorized the components of job satisfaction are intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction. One aspect of job satisfaction that focuses on aspects connected to the work is the type of work, the variety of responsibilities, and the required degree of knowledge. It is a gauge of an individual's level of happiness with the intrinsic features of the work; extrinsic satisfaction is associated with the job's external features, such as pay, opportunities for advancement, supervision, and working conditions (Weiss *et al.*, 1967). Eight factors are listed by Spector (2022), in his more in-depth study of job satisfaction coworkers (our colleagues), benefits (such as labor and health insurance, and other benefits), working conditions, nature of the job itself (the tasks we perform), and job-relatedness of the job (the job-relatedness of the tasks we perform).

Job Insecurity

Job insecurity is a personal experience resulting from a thorough assessment of one's present workplace. It shows up as a worker's worry about possible dangers at work combined with a negative view of the chances of these circumstances getting better (Shao *et al.*, 2022). The perception by an individual of a threat to the continuation of their present employment circumstances is known as job insecurity (De Witte *et al.*, 2023). It is a certain experience that workers will have all of their careers (Langerak *et al.*, 2022). Different subjective interpretations of the same objective conditions, including the uncertainty of work retention or the possible loss of some job features, and the difference between expectations and actuality can lead to this insecurity (De Cuyper *et al.*, 2021). Finally, the fear of losing one's job is what is meant by job insecurity (Llosa *et al.*, 2023). Generally speaking, work instability is divided into two dimensions: quantitative and qualitative. These two dimensions are conceptually and practically different even if they are constructively the same (De Witte *et al.*, 2023). Whereas quantitative job insecurity is concerned with the fear of losing one's present job, qualitative job insecurity is concerned with the possibility that one's job may alter negatively (De Cuyper *et al.*, 2021).

Affective Commitment

Affective commitment is employees who have emotional ties and help achieve organisational goals because they know and understand the goals and values of the organisation (Shao *et al.*, 2022). Affective commitment is a part of organisational commitment. In theory, organisational commitment is divided into three concepts, namely a desire as affective commitment, a need as continuance commitment, and an

obligation as normative commitment to maintain a working relationship in the organisation (Meyer & Allen, 1991). This affective commitment refers to the emotions that merge with the organisation and encourage them to stay in it (Koo *et al.*, 2020). Employees will have a strong desire to stay in the organisation because they have a strong affective commitment and relate themselves more closely to the goals of the organisation (Gün *et al.*, 2021). Affective commitment is an emotional state in which committed employees recognise, care about and enjoy being part of the organisation (Jiatong *et al.*, 2022). Affective commitment has three conditions, namely a state in which a person is emotionally attached, identified and involved in the organisation (Meyer & Allen, 1991).

Job Performance

Job performance is work achievement as the behaviour and work results of employees to achieve organisational goals within a certain period, which is conducive to improving organisational efficiency (Shao *et al.*, 2022), and how efficiently employees can complete their work *pekerjaannya* (Torlak & Kuzey, 2019). Job performance is defined as the quantity and quality resulting from the work done by individuals or groups (Dinc *et al.*, 2018; Katebi *et al.*, 2022). The main objective of any company is job performance. The company's total income reflects the quality and quantity of its employees' work and the results of their work, or their performance (C. C. Lee *et al.*, 2023).

Task job performance scale and contextual job performance scale are two subscales of the work performance dimension (Kalia & Bhardwaj, 2019; Shao *et al.*, 2022). The task job performance scale measures employee task completion and attainment of organizational goals at the technical level of the organization using production quality and productivity gains (Kleszczewska *et al.*, 2019; Shao *et al.*, 2022). Then, the contextual job performance scale includes interpersonal factors and volitional motivation. There are five aspects, namely, employees need to take initiative to complete work outside working hours, enthusiasm for work, cooperation with others, implementation of organisational rules and support of organisational goals (Gaye & Cavide, 2019).

Relationship Between Variables

Relationship between Transformational leadership and Job satisfaction

Research on Indonesian port workers indicates that job satisfaction is benefited by transformative leadership (Eliyana *et al.*, 2019). The research findings presented here are consistent with those of other studies, which demonstrate that transformational leadership significantly and favorably affects job satisfaction (Al Draij & Al Saed, 2023; Anindita & Senjaya, 2020; Moin *et al.*, 2021; Nielsen *et al.*, 2022). These studies include studies on pharmaceutical employees, mining companies, service organizations, and general companies. The same outcomes are shown by mergers and acquisitions in other research on personnel with restructuring situations in companies (Luu & Phan, 2020). Studies that yield contradictory conclusions, however, claim that job happiness and transformational leadership are unrelated (Taduvana *et al.*, 2022). The hypothesis is thus put out based on the findings of the studies mentioned above:

H1: Transformational leadership has a positive effect on job satisfaction.

Relationship between Transformational leadership and Job Insecurity

Research on the relationship between the influence of transformational leadership and job insecurity is almost not found in journals, so references on this subject are limited. Research in the Netherlands on a large scale involving 89 thousand respondents showed a positive influence, where for permanent employees the influence was stronger than for temporary employees (van Vuuren *et al.*, 2019). Other research in China shows a negative relationship (Qian *et al.*, 2022). However, other studies show no effect (Çiçek & Kılınç, 2021; Hallo *et al.*, 2020). From the results of the above studies, the hypothesis is hereby proposed:

H2: Transformational leadership has a negative effect on job insecurity.

Relationship between Transformational leadership and Job performance

General speaking, leadership will improve job performance (Nugroho & Pudiastuti, 2021). Other research in multiple nations with different fields also demonstrates that the findings are consistent (Indradewa *et al.*, 2020; Jiatong *et al.*, 2022; C. C. Lee *et al.*, 2023; Manzoor *et al.*, 2019; Shao *et al.*, 2022; Sürücü *et al.*, 2022). According to several studies on workers in restructuring, mergers, and acquisitions, transformational leadership significantly and favorably affects job performance (Luu & Phan, 2020). The conclusion of several studies presented by Eliyana *et al.* (2019) was that transformative leadership had no bearing on job performance. Proposed is the following hypothesis based on the findings of the studies mentioned above:

H3: Transformational leadership has a positive effect on job performance.

Relationship between Transformational leadership and Affective Commitment

Research on employees of companies with hotel areas, service industry, manufacturing industry, high-tech industry, government agencies, educational institutions in China shows that transformational leadership has a positive influence on Affective Commitment (Shao *et al.*, 2022). The research results from Shao *et al.* (2022) above are in line with the results of other studies, for example research on employees of ports, hotels, private companies, and hospitals which show that transformational leadership has a positive effect on Affective Commitment afektif (Alnahedh & Alrashdan, 2021; Eliyana *et al.*, 2019; Indradewa *et al.*, 2020; Jiatong *et al.*, 2022; Park *et al.*, 2022). In other studies on employees with company conditions in restructuring, mergers, and acquisitions show the same results (Luu & Phan, 2020). From the results of the above studies, the hypothesis is hereby proposed:

H4: Transformational leadership has a positive effect on affective commitment.

Relationship between Job satisfaction and Job performance

Research on employees at ports in Indonesia shows that job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on job performance (Eliyana *et al.*, 2019). The results of this study are consistent with those of previous research where job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on job performance kinerja (Alwali & Alwali, 2022; Gazi *et al.*, 2022; Kustiawan *et al.*, 2022). However, other studies show that job satisfaction has a negative effect on employee job performance (Goetz & Wald, 2022). From the explanation above, which shows that there are differences in research results, but generally more mention a positive and significant effect, so this hypothesis is proposed:

H5: Job satisfaction has a positive effect on job performance.

Relationship between Job insecurity and Job performance

In a large-scale Dutch study involving 89 thousand employee respondents, it was found that job insecurity reduced job performance, and even had no advantage for company productivity (van Vuuren *et al.*, 2019). The negative effect of job insecurity can also cause worse impacts (Adekiya, 2023). These results are confirmed in other studies with similar results (Qian *et al.*, 2022; Riania & Nisa, 2022; Shao *et al.*, 2022; Syafitri *et al.*, 2022). From the results of the above studies, the hypothesis is hereby proposed:

H6: Job insecurity has a negative effect on job performance.

Relationship between Affective Commitment and Job performance

Research on employees of companies with hotel areas, service industries, manufacturing industries, high-tech industries, government agencies, educational institutions in China shows that Affective Commitment has a positive influence on job performance (Shao *et al.*, 2022). The research results from Shao *et al.* (2022) mentioned above are in line with the results of other studies which show a positive and significant effect (Gün *et al.*, 2021; Nauman *et al.*, 2021; Tjahjono *et al.*, 2020; Wayoi *et al.*, 2021). However, other studies show that Affective Commitment has a negative effect on employee job performance (Goetz & Wald, 2022). From the results of the above studies, a hypothesis is hereby proposed:

H7: Affective Commitment has a positive effect on job performance.

The Role of Mediating Variables in the Relationship of Exogenous Variables to Endogenous Variables

Earlier, it was clarified that the independent variable, transformational leadership (X), has a direct and considerable impact on the dependent variable, job performance (Y). Furthermore, it has been demonstrated that there is a positive correlation between the measure of transformational leadership (X) and the mediating factors of work satisfaction (Z1), job insecurity (Z2), and Affective Commitment (Z3). Likewise, these intermediary factors have a direct impact on job performance (Y). Eliyana *et al.* (2019) demonstrates that organizational commitment and job satisfaction play a beneficial impact in enhancing job performance. Alwali & Alwali (2022) demonstrate that job satisfaction while acting as a mediator, can exert a substantial and beneficial impact. Furthermore, research conducted by Qian *et al.* (2022) and Shao *et al.* (2022) indicates that mediation exacerbates the adverse impact of job instability on job performance. Moreover, using the explanation provided earlier, the subsequent hypothesis is put forward:

H8a: Job insecurity negatively mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and job performance.

H8b: Affective Commitment positively mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and job performance.

H8c: Job satisfaction positively mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and job performance.

H8d: The total effect of the indirect relationship of transformational leadership on job performance has a positive effect.

Based on the hypothesis explanation, the proposed research model is:

Figure 1: Model of Research

Source: (Eliyana *et al.*, 2019) and (Shao *et al.*, 2022) with adjustments

METHODS

This research is a study of the perceptions of manufacturing employee respondents about five research variables: transformational leadership, job satisfaction, job insecurity, affective commitment, and performance. Information is collected by means of a Google Forms online survey. This survey employs the Likert scale measurement interval of 1–5, where strongly disagree is represented by number 1 and strongly agree by number 5. Based on the five variables under investigation, namely transformational leadership, the questionnaire was developed using the “Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire for Transformational Leadership” with 15 Indicators, an adaptation from Avolio & Bass (2004) and Eliyana *et al.* (2019). The nine-indicator “Job Satisfaction Scale (JSC)” adaption from Spector (2022) served as the basis for measuring the job satisfaction factors. Using adaptations of the Job Insecurity Scale (JIS), namely the original scale from De Witte *et al.* (2015) and the “Qualitative Job Insecurity Scale (QJIS)” which has six indicators and two dimensions job insecurity variables were measured (Blotenberg & Richter, 2020; De Witte *et al.*, 2015; Shao *et al.*, 2022). The six-indicator affective commitment variable measurement was modified from O’ *et al.* (1986). The two dimensions and eleven statements of the performance variable measurement were taken from Koopmans *et al.* (2014). There are 47 statements in all recommended as indicators.

This survey was conducted from November 2023 to January 2024. In this survey, the respondent population was manufacturing employees. The sampling method uses homogeneous purposive sampling with the sampling criteria being only employees implementing the production process, namely operators and level one leaders. The production operator employees are permanent employees at PT UTAC Manufacturing Services Indonesia and PT SHARP Semikonduktor Indonesia located in the Karawang industrial area, Indonesia. These two companies are large multinational semiconductor companies and are well-known as semiconductor pioneers in Indonesia. In order to determine the number of variable indicators, the minimum number of respondents is 235. This figure is multiplied by five, as indicated by Memon *et al.* (2020). The survey was conducted between November 2023 and January 2024.

This research approach is quantitative deductive, where the research will develop hypotheses from existing theories, build from general to specific matters, and explain causal relationships between variables. The data analysis method used is the Structural Equation Model (SEM) with the Partial Least Square (PLS) type of choice, which is referred to as PLS-SEM. The reason for using PLS-SEM is because partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) is a modern multivariate analysis technique with a proven ability to estimate theoretically established causal relationship models and has been adopted in construction management research for two decades (Zeng *et al.*, 2021). In PLS-SEM, there are three evaluations carried out, the evaluation of the measurement model, the evaluation of the structural model, and the evaluation of the goodness of fit of the model (Hair *et al.*, 2019). PLS-SEM data processing uses Smart-PLS 4 software.

The research began by conducting a pretest survey to test the validity and reliability of the indicators in the questionnaire. The survey respondents were 30 people, which was the minimum pretest requirement (Perneger *et al.*, 2015). In evaluating the measurement model for the pretest to obtain the validity and reliability of the relationship between reflective indicators, the evaluation reference for validity is testing the loading factor (LF) value > 0.70 , Average Variance Extracted (AVE) > 0.50 . Meanwhile, for reliability, the Cronbach's Alpha (CA) value is > 0.70 and the Composite Reliability (CR) value is > 0.70 (Hair *et al.*, 2019).

Pretest survey data on the first 30 respondents showed that five variables with 47 indicators showed that there were 6 variables with validity values below 0.70, namely TL.06 (0.151), TL.09 (0.050), TL.12 (0.292), AC.2 (0.100), AC.3 (0.044), and JS.02 (0.676). Thus, a second pretest is needed, where a correction is carried out by eliminating the six indicators, so that the number of indicators becomes only 41. The test results show that all 41 indicators from the 5 variables meet the factor loading value > 0.70 , so they can be declared valid. Reliability testing with Cronbach's alpha showed the results AC = 0.888, JI = 0.937, JP = 0.792, JS = 0.951, and TL = 0.973, with values above the reference > 0.70 . For the composite reliability test, AC = 0.924, JI = 0.950, JP = 0.975, JS = 0.959, and TL = 0.976 with a reference above 0.70. The next stage of the AVE test obtained AC = 0.753, JI = 0.762, JP = 0.783, JS = 0.748, and TL = 0.772, with values above the reference > 0.50 . Thus, a total of 41 indicators from 5 variables have met the requirements to be declared valid and reliable. The minimum number of respondents required is a minimum of $41 \times 5 = 205$ respondents, where the available responses are 210 respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Results

After fulfilling the validity and reliability of the variable indicators in the pretest, testing was carried out on the entire sample of 210 respondents using SmartPLS4 data processing software. The profile of research respondents is permanent employees, with a composition of 97 percent operator level and 3 percent of first level leaders (supervising directly on the production line) consisting of 43percent men and 57 percent women. 99 percent of them are married and 1 percent are not married. Age 18 years-25 years is 2 percent, age 26 years-35 years is 61 percent, age 36 years-40 years is 18 percent, and age 40 years and over is 19 percent. 93 percent of employees have a high school/vocational education, 4 percent have a D1-D3 education, and

3percent have a bachelor's degree. Then for a work period of 1 year - less than 10 years it is 6 percent, a work period of 10 years - less than 15 years is 60 percent, 15 years - less than 20 years is 20 percent, and more than 20 years is 14 percent.

Next, for the first stage, an outer model measurement test was carried out on the reflective indicators to obtain validity and reliability. Based on evaluation of outer loading results above, it can be stated that the transformational leadership variable (X), job satisfaction variable (Z1), job insecurity variable (Z2), affective commitment variable (Z3) has an external loading value above the reference value of 0.70, so it can be stated that the 41 measurement items of each variable are valid to measure what should be measured by the 5 variables. For the reliability based on Cronbach's alpha for the 5 variables has a value range of 0.882 to 0.950 > 0.70 and based on the composite reliability (rho-c) shows a value range of 0.911 to 0.977 > 0.70, so it can be said that it meets the reliability requirements. See Figure 2. Diagram of the validity and reliability test.

Figure 2: Measurement Model Evaluation Diagram

Source: SMART-PLS Data Processing

Next, we continue examining the discriminant validity of the Fornell Larcker criterion with the aim of a form of evaluation to ensure that a variable is theoretically different and proven empirically or by statistical testing. Fornell Larker's criterion is that the square root of the average variance extracted by a construct must be greater than the correlation between that construct and other constructs (Hair *et al.*, 2019). To obtain more sensitive and accurate discriminant validity, heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT) testing was carried out. Based on Table 1 bellow, the results of the HTMT pair of all variables show values from 0.104 to 0.332 < 0.90, so that the discriminant validity is fulfilled. Thus, we can say that the validity and reliability of 5 variables with 41 reflective indicators have met the requirements of the reference value of validity and reliability.

Table 1: Heterotrait Monotrait Rasio (HTMT)

Variable	Transformational Leadership (X)	Job Satisfaction (Z1)	Job Insecurity (Z2)	Job Performance (Y)	Affective Commitment (Z3)
Transformational Leadership (X)	0,803				
Job Satisfaction (Z1)	0,322	0,841			
Job Insecurity (Z2)	-0,541	-0,183	0,794		
Job Performance (Y)	0,328	0,850	-0,076	0,890	
Affective Commitment (Z3)	0,287	0,759	-0,041	0,819	0,914

Source: SMART-PLS Data Processing

After fulfilling the validity and reliability and fulfilling the multicollinearity check, we proceed to the model construction evaluation stage to answer the hypothesis.

Table 2: Hypothesis Testing

HYPOTHESIS	Direct Effect	Path Coefisients	T-Stats.	P-Value	95% Confident Interval Path Coefisients		F-Square	Description
					Lower Limit	Upper Limit		
H1	Transformational Leadership (X) has a positive effect on Job Satisfaction (Z1)	0,322	5,118	0,005	0,197	0,441	0,115	Data support the hypothesis
H2	Transformational Leadership (X) has a negative effect on Job Insecurity (Z2)	-0,541	6,718	0,000	-0,687	0,441	0,413	Data support the hypothesis
H3	Transformational Leadership (X) has a positive effect on Job Performance (Y)	0,090	2,486	0,013	0,015	0,157	0,026	Data support the hypothesis
H4	Transformational Leadership (X) has a positive effect on Affective Commitment (Z3)	0,287	4,251	0,000	0,153	0,419	0,090	Data support the hypothesis
H5	Job Satisfaction (Z1) has a positive effect on Job Performance (Y)	0,548	9,187	0,000	0,423	0,658	0,601	Data support the hypothesis
H6	Job Insecurity (Z) has a negative effect on Job Performance (Y)	0,089	2,408	0,016	0,013	0,155	0,026	Data does not support the hypothesis
H7	Affective Commitment (Z3) has a positive effect on Job Performance (Y)	0,381	6,259	0,000	0,267	0,506		Data support the hypothesis
HYPOTHESIS	Indirect Effect	Indirect Effect	T-Stats.	P-Value	Lower Limit	Upper Limit	Upsilon V	Description
H8.a	Job Insecurity (Z2) negatively mediates the relationship of Transformational Leadership (X) on Job Performance (Y)	-0,048	2,291	0,022	0,197	0,441	0,002	Data support the hypothesis
H8.b	Affective Commitment (Z3) positively mediates the relationship of Transformational Leadership (X1) to Job Performance (Y)	0,109	3,352	0,001	-0,687	0,441	0,013	Data support the hypothesis
H8.c	Job Satisfaction (Z1) positively mediates the relationship of Transformational Leadership (X) to Job Performance (Y)	0,176	4,248	0,000	0,015	0,157	0,031	Data support the hypothesis
H8.d	Total positive indirect effect of Transformational Leadership on Job Performance (Y)	0,238	4,101	0,000	0,153	0,419	0,059	Data support the hypothesis

Source: SMART-PLS Data Processing

References for hypothesis testing between variables begin by assessing the strength and direction of the relationship between variables, where the path coefficient value is > 0.00 (positive); Checking 5 percent significance with $n > 200$, it is known that $t\text{-statistics} > t\text{-table } 1.976$ (significant) and $p\text{-value} < 0.005$ (significant). For effect size, use $f\text{-square}$ for direct influence with $f\text{-square}$ criteria of 0.02 low, 0.15 moderate, and 0.35 high (Hair *et al.*, 2021), while the $f\text{-square}$ mediation test with reference values is 0.02 as low, 0.075 as moderate, and 0.175 as high (Gaskin *et al.*, 2023; Lachowicz *et al.*, 2018).

Based on table 1 above, for hypothesis testing for direct influence, namely for hypothesis H1 which shows that transformational leadership has a positive effect on job satisfaction, it shows positive results (path coefficient 0.322), significant (T-Statistic value $5.118 > 1.976$ and P-Value value $0.000 < 0.05$), with an impact towards moderate ($F\text{-Square } 0.115 > 0.02$ but < 0.15). This data supports the hypothesis, so the hypothesis can be accepted. For the hypothesis H2 which states that transformational leadership has a negative effect on job insecurity, it is confirmed by the results which show negative results (path path coefficients -0.322), significant (T-Statistic value $6.718 > 1.976$), significant (P-Value value $0.000 < 0.05$), with a strong impact ($F\text{-Square } 0.413 > 0.35$). This data supports the hypothesis, so the hypothesis can be accepted.

The hypothesis H3 which states that transformational leadership has a positive effect on employee performance is confirmed by positive results (path coefficients 0.090), significant (T-Statistic value $2.486 > 1.976$ and P-Value $0.013 < 0.05$), with a low impact ($F\text{-Square } 0.026 > 0.02$). This data supports the hypothesis, so the hypothesis can be accepted. Hypothesis H4 which states that transformational leadership has a positive effect on the affective commitment to work of production employees shows positive results (path coefficient 0.287), significant (T-Statistic value $4.251 > 1.976$ and a P-Value value of $0.000 < 0.05$), with a low to moderate impact ($F\text{-Square } 0.090 > 0.02$). This data supports the hypothesis, so the hypothesis can be accepted. Then for hypothesis H5 which states that job satisfaction has an effect positive results with respect to employee performance show positive results (path coefficient 0.548), significant (T-Statistic value $9.187 > 1.976$ and P-Value value $0.000 < 0.05$), with a high impact ($F\text{-Square } 0.601 > 0.35$). This data supports the hypothesis, so the hypothesis can be accepted.

However, hypothesis H6 which states that job insecurity has a negative effect on employee performance shows positive results (path coefficient 0.381), significant (T-Statistic value $6.259 > 1.976$ and P-Value $0.000 < 0.05$), with a low impact ($F\text{-Square } 0.292 > 0.35$). This data does not support the hypothesis, so the hypothesis cannot be accepted. The results of testing hypothesis H7 which states that the influence of affective commitment on employee performance shows positive results (path coefficient 0.381), significant (T-Statistic value $6.259 > 1.976$ and P-Value value $0.000 < 0.05$), with a high impact ($F\text{-Square } 0.292 > 0.35$). This data supports the hypothesis, so the hypothesis can be accepted.

Next, we examine the influence of the indirect relationship between hypotheses H8a, H8b, H8c, and H8d. The results of the hypothesis test H8a which states that job insecurity mediates transformational leadership on performance shows a negative relationship (path coefficient -0.048), meaning that the less job insecurity, the higher the performance. The significance results show significant results (T-Statistics value

2.291 > 1.976 and P-Value 0.022 < 0.05). However, the effect size has a low impact (upsilon v 0.002 < 0.02). This data supports the hypothesis, so the hypothesis can be accepted.

For the hypothesis H8b which states that affective commitment positively mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and performance, it is confirmed from the results positive relationship (patch coefficient 0.109), significant (T-Statistic value 3.352 > 1.976 and P-Value 0.000 < 0.05). However, the effect size measured from upsilon v shows that affective commitment has a low impact (upsilon v 0.002 < 0.02). This data supports the hypothesis, so the hypothesis can be accepted.

Then the hypothesis H8c which states that job satisfaction positively mediates the relationship between transformational leadership and performance is confirmed from the results the positive work relationship is positive (patch coefficient 0.176), significant (T-Statistic value 4.248 > 1.976 and P-Value value 0.000 < 0.05), and has a moderate impact (upsilon v 0.031 > 0.02 but < 0.075). This data supports the hypothesis, so the hypothesis can be accepted.

Then finally, examining the results of the H8d hypothesis for the total indirect influence of transformational leadership on performance shows a positive relationship (patch coefficient 0.109), significant (T-Statistic value 3.352 > 1.976 and P-Value 0.000 < 0.05), and low impact (upsilon v 0.0013 > 0.02). This data supports the hypothesis, so the hypothesis can be accepted.

From the explanation above it can be concluded that the results of testing the hypothesis of a direct relationship H1, H2, H3, H4, H5, and H7 data support the hypothesis so that the hypothesis can be accepted. Only the data does not support hypothesis H6 so the hypothesis cannot be accepted. Meanwhile, the indirect relationship H8a, H8b, H8c, and H8d all show results that support the hypothesis, so the hypothesis can be accepted.

Figure 3: Structural Model Evaluation Diagram (Path Coefficients & T-Values)

Source: SMART-PLS 4 Data Processing

The final phase is assessing the model's quality with the PLS Predict, R Square, Q Square, Standardized Root Mean Residual (SRMR), and R Square tests.

Table 3: R Square, Q-Square, and SRMR

Variable	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted	Q-Square	SRMR
Performance (Y)	0.800	0.796	0.099	0.067
	Strong > 0.75	Strong > 0.75	Moderate 0.00 < 0.099 < 0.50	Fit < 0.080

Source: SMART-PLS 4 Data Processing

To find out how much endogenous variables can be explained by exogenous variables, the R-Square test is needed, where the reference values are 0.25 (low), 0.50 (moderate), and 0.75 (high) (Hair *et al.*, 2019). Based on table 6 above, for R-Square it is known that the endogenous variable performance (Y) has an R-Square of 80 percent > 75 percent (strong relationship) meaning that it can be explained by the exogenous variables job satisfaction (Z1), job insecurity (Z2) and affective commitment (Z3) is 80 percent, while 20 percent is explained by other variables not in this study. As for Q-Square, the relevance value of the prediction model for the exogenous influence of job satisfaction (Z1), job insecurity (Z2) and affective commitment (Z3) on endogenous performance (Y) is 0.099 > 0.00 or 9.9 percent so it can be said to have the influence of good model relevance (Hair *et al.*, 2019). However, it should be noted that predictive ability only has a moderate influence. Next, we examined the Standardized Root Mean Residual (SRMR) with a reference value of < 0.08 as the fit model (Hair *et al.*, 2021), and the result is 0.067 < 0.08, so it can be stated that the model is fit. From the explanation above, it can be concluded that based on the R-Square, Q-Square and SRMR tests, this structural model meets the model fit requirements.

Next, the predictive power or PLS Predict is studied by comparing PLS with the Linear Model where the PLS model is said to have predictive power if the RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error) or MAE (Mean Absolute Error) size of the PLS model is lower than the linear regression model, then is said to have a strong influence (Hair *et al.*, 2019). PLS Predict test results show that the PLS-SEM Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) measure has 36 indicators out of 41 indicators lower than RSME LM and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) has 31 indicators out of 41 indicators lower than MAE LM, so it can be declared PLS -SEM has better predictive power than LM with maximum power.

DISCUSSION

This research explores and tests the influence of transformational leadership on performance through several mediating variables, namely job satisfaction, job insecurity, and affective commitment. In this discussion we will discuss the direct influence represented by H1 - H7 and the indirect influence represented by H8a, H8b, H8c, and H8d.

Hypotheses H1, H3, and H4 have been confirmed that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on job satisfaction, performance, and affective commitment. As stated by (Bass & Bass, 2008) who state that transformational leaders must be able to motivate their followers to go beyond their own interests for the good of the group, organization or society to achieve goals, where followers will be able to achieve and actualize themselves because they are encouraged to be able to face challenges. themselves. In this way, companies in practice can make efforts to

improve transformational leadership by, among other things, providing information and regular meetings about important company values, company goals, providing information on business developments and providing optimism for the company's future. It is hoped that these efforts will transform the values of transformational leadership, as stated by Robbins & Judge (2022) that transformational leadership inspires their followers to place their interests for the good of the organization, and they can have a tremendous influence on their followers. Empirical research results from different industries and countries show positive and significant results of transformational leadership on job satisfaction (Al Draij & Al Saed, 2023; Anindita & Senjaya, 2020; Eliyana *et al.*, 2019; Luu & Phan, 2020; Moin *et al.*, 2021; Nielsen *et al.*, 2022); positive influence on performance (Indradewa *et al.*, 2020; Jiatong *et al.*, 2022; S. Lee *et al.*, 2023; Luu & PhaSn, 2020; Manzoor *et al.*, 2019; Shao *et al.*, 2022; Sürücü *et al.*, 2022); and positive influence on affective commitment (Alnahedh & Alrashdan, 2021; Eliyana *et al.*, 2019; Jiatong *et al.*, 2022; Luu & Phan, 2020; Park *et al.*, 2022; Shao *et al.*, 2022).

Then, hypothesis H2 has been confirmed that transformational leadership has a negative and significant effect on job insecurity. The implication of negative influence is that if the negative variables of transformational leadership are reduced and continue to be increased, then employee job insecurity will decrease. According to Llosa *et al.* (2023), job insecurity is understood as the fear of losing one's job, so the ability to manage employee perceptions is important. This is important, because those who work are direct employees of the production department, so providing information about the continuity and development of the company is very important. In the production department, if there is a transfer of work, the reasons must be explained and adequate training must be given to avoid suspicion that causes fear of being dismissed. Previous research showed different results, namely from van Vuuren *et al.* (2019), showing a positive relationship, while the research results of Hallo *et al.* (2020) and Çiçek & Kılınc, (2021) stated there was no effect. Similar results are from Qian *et al.* (2022) which states a negative and significant relationship. And the results of the research we conducted show a negative and significant relationship.

In H5 we can see how job satisfaction has a positive and significant effect on performance. The company has made efforts to maintain and increase job satisfaction by making employees feel comfortable in their work and providing appreciation for the results of their work. Formal communication in regular meetings will really help bridge employee dissatisfaction about something. The company ensures that employees' career paths are in good condition and has programs for level advancement or other promotions. Benchmarking activities for composites and benefits with neighboring companies in the same or different businesses in one area are important to ensure that company benefits are not below market or too high. Meanwhile, this is in line with the results of previous research which also shows the positive and significant influence of job satisfaction on performance (Alwali & Alwali, 2022; Eliyana *et al.*, 2019b; Gazi *et al.*, 2022; Kustiawan *et al.*, 2022).

Empirically, job insecurity has a negative effect on performance, where the empirical results of previous studies show a negative effect (Adekiya, 2023; Qian *et al.*, 2022; Riania & Nisa, 2022; Shao *et al.*, 2022; Syafitri *et al.*, 2022; van Vuuren *et al.*, 2019). However, the results of testing hypothesis H6 in this study show that job insecurity has a positive effect on performance. This can be explained that for survivors employees unsafe conditions give them additional efforts to improve their performance thereby

providing a sense of security in their work. A reference can be seen in the research results of Shoss *et al.* (2020) which states that people who are afraid of losing their jobs actually try to focus on their work and have high hopes that this will be known and appreciated by their superiors. Other research also states that job insecurity will increase employee motivation to improve performance only if their motivation is low or they feel high distributive justice (Koen *et al.*, 2020).

Hypothesis H7 shows that affective commitment has a positive and significant effect on performance. In affective commitment, as Jiatong *et al.* (2022) mention, it is an emotional state in which committed employees recognize, care about, and are happy to be part of the organization. In this way, the company carries out activities to instill corporate cultural values. Employees can understand the company's vision and mission, feel part of the company, and are proud to work for the company. These results are in line with the results of previous research which shows the positive influence of affective commitment on performance (Gün *et al.*, 2021; Nauman *et al.*, 2021; Shao *et al.*, 2022; Wayoi *et al.*, 2021).

Furthermore, in examining the indirect relationship, the test of hypothesis H8a where job insecurity mediates transformational leadership on performance shows a negative and significant relationship. This is in line with the results of previous research which showed a negative influence (Qian *et al.*, 2022; van Vuuren *et al.*, 2019). Negative influence means that the less job insecurity, the higher the performance. This negative relationship has significant strength, so companies can add things to improve transformational leadership, so as to reduce the negative influence of job insecurity, and ultimately improve performance and vice versa. In line with the findings of Shao *et al.* (2022) efforts to reduce job insecurity have been associated with improvements in performance.

Empirical research results show the positive influence of transformational leadership on performance (Eliyana *et al.*, 2019; 2020; Jiatong *et al.*, 2022; S. Lee *et al.*, 2023; Manzoor *et al.*, 2019; Shao *et al.*, 2022; Sürücü *et al.*, 2022) and towards affective commitment (Alnahedh & Alrashdan, 2021; Eliyana *et al.*, 2019; Jiatong *et al.*, 2022; Luu & Phan, 2020; Park *et al.*, 2022; Shao *et al.*, 2022). In testing the specific indirect influence hypothesis, H8b is tested where affective commitment mediates the positive and significant relationship between transformational leadership and performance. Opportunities for improvement by increasing transformational leadership, joint affective commitment to improve performance. This is in line with previous research that affective commitment has a positive and significant effect on performance (Gün *et al.*, 2021; Nauman *et al.*, 2021; Shao *et al.*, 2022; Wayoi *et al.*, 2021).

Job satisfaction as a mediating variable in the results of hypothesis H8c shows the positive influence of the relationship between transformational leadership and performance. Empirical research results show that transformational leadership has a positive effect on job satisfaction (Al Draij & Al Saed, 2023; Anindita & Senjaya, 2020; Luu & Phan, 2020; Moin *et al.*, 2021; Nielsen *et al.*, 2022); and job satisfaction also has a positive effect on performance (Alwali & Alwali, 2022; Gazi *et al.*, 2022; Kustiawan *et al.*, 2022). Companies can still increase the power of transformational leadership and job satisfaction, so that this positive and significant influence can be maximized. The results of hypothesis testing H8d have shown that there is a total indirect relationship between transformational leadership and performance. The above results of exposure to specific and total indirect effects have confirmed the proposed

hypothesis H8d. Previous research results empirically show positive results (Eliyana *et al.*, 2019b; Jiatong *et al.*, 2022; S. Lee *et al.*, 2023; Manzoor *et al.*, 2019; Shao *et al.*, 2022; Sürücü *et al.*, 2022).

CONCLUSION

Research on the influence of transformational leadership on performance through the mediation of job satisfaction, job insecurity, and affective commitment in semiconductor manufacturing companies with production employee respondents has resulted in several conclusions, namely: First, of the total of 7 hypotheses proposed for a direct relationship, there are 6 confirmed to have a relationship. positive and significant and 1 has a negative and significant relationship.

Transformational leadership in the direct influence relationship model was confirmed positively and significantly on the mediating variables of job satisfaction and affective commitment, and on the exogenous variable performance. However, the magnitude of the impact is low and tends to be moderate. However, the hypothesis assumption H6 states that job insecurity has a negative and significant influence on performance, which the data does not support because it shows a positive and significant influence.

The influence is great, so if transformational leadership is implemented well and improved, it will reduce the impact of job insecurity and even make it positive. The results of the magnitude of the impact are low and moderate, the Company can still make systematic efforts with good analysis to improve the transformational leadership of production employees so that it increases, and it has even been confirmed that reducing job insecurity will produce a strong magnitude of impact.

The second conclusion from the 4 indirect influence hypotheses produces 3 positive and significant influences, and 1 gives a negative and significant influence. In an indirect relationship, transformational leadership is mediated by job satisfaction and affective commitment to performance showing a positive and significant relationship with low to moderate impact magnitude.

This is in line with the total influence of the indirect relationship between transformational leadership and performance which shows a positive and significant relationship, as well as a moderate impact. Meanwhile, mediation through performance shows a negative and significant relationship with a moderate impact size. Companies must be able to improve this mediating variable in mediating transformational leadership on performance.

In this research, it has been confirmed that transformational leadership has a positive and significant influence on production employees at the UTAC and SHARP semiconductor manufacturing companies.

As far as the author knows, this is new for semiconductor industry employee respondents in Indonesia, but there are limitations that require broader research on semiconductor companies in other countries, so that it is hoped to produce better and more comprehensive results.

Another limitation is the impact of the exogenous variable transformational leadership with multiple mediating variables on the endogenous variable performance in direct and indirect relationships, which apparently only produces a low and moderate impact size, so it does not provide comprehensive results.

Research on adding other variables or developing the variables in this research will be useful to cover the shortcomings of this research. Limitations in this research also include measuring performance using individual perceptions of employees in carrying out work, so it is subjective. So in future research, performance measures should be more objective.

Academic research results can provide scientific contributions by exploring the relationship between transformational leadership and performance through the mediation of job satisfaction, job insecurity, and affective commitment. The results obtained can provide additional knowledge and insight into these research variables in the fields of management, organization and social sciences in general. The results of this research can be a reference for subsequent research interested in the same topic.

This research provides managerial implications, firstly the relationship between transformational leadership and job insecurity is directly and indirectly confirmed to produce negative results. With these results, the company must make the recommended efforts to continue and improve them, including the latest and regular information that provides job security, technology training and new systems so that employees do not feel worried about losing their jobs and or being dismissed at any time.

Companies need to accommodate the affective commitment variable to be increased by clarifying the vision and mission and distribution of work for all employees to understand, so that employees understand and have company values, and feel proud to work for the company.

Second, companies are required to maintain and improve key performance indicators (KPI) for production so that employees can easily understand them. All parties are expected to contribute to achieving the target KPI.

An important factor is also the implementation of fair performance appraisals and career paths that are conveyed and understood by employees. To avoid feelings of job insecurity and increase job satisfaction, companies must pay attention to compensation and benefits through market surveys for similar business organizations or comparisons within one industrial area.

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Reference

- 1) Adekiya, A. (2023). Perceived job insecurity and task performance: what aspect of performance is related to which facet of job insecurity. *Current Psychology*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-023-04408-4>
- 2) Al Draj, F., & Al Saed, R. (2023). "Mediating role of employee empowerment for transformational leadership and job satisfaction." *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 21(1), 59–68. [https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.21\(1\).2023.06](https://doi.org/10.21511/ppm.21(1).2023.06)
- 3) Ali, B. J., & Anwar, G. (2021). An Empirical Study of Employees' Motivation and its Influence Job Satisfaction. <https://doi.org/10.22161/ijebm.5.2>

- 4) Alnahedh, M., & Alrashdan, A. (2021). To downsize or not to downsize: when and how does corporate downsizing create long-term value? *Management Research Review*, 44(11), 1539–1564. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MRR-09-2020-0552>
- 5) Alwali, J., & Alwali, W. (2022). The relationship between emotional intelligence, transformational leadership, and performance: a test of the mediating role of job satisfaction. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 43(6), 928–952. <https://doi.org/10.1108/LODJ-10-2021-0486>
- 6) Anindita, R., & Senjaya, V. (2020). The Role of Transformational Leadership and Organizational Culture Towards Organizational Commitment Through Job Satisfaction Among Mining Industry Employees. *Journal of Applied Management (JAM)*, 18(4). <https://doi.org/10.21776/ub.jam.2020.018.04.15>
- 7) Avolio, B., & Bass, B. (2004). *Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire: Manual and Sempler Set. In Manual and Sample Set.*
- 8) Bass, B., & Bass, R. (2008). *The Bass Handbook of Leadership Theory, Research, and Managerial Applications (4th ed.)*. Free Press A Division of Simon & Schuster, Inc.
- 9) Blotenberg, I., & Richter, A. (2020). Validation of the QJIM: A measure of qualitative job insecurity. In *Work and Stress (Vol. 34, Issue 4, pp. 406–417)*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02678373.2020.1719553>
- 10) Busari, A. H., Khan, S. N., Abdullah, S. M., & Mughal, Y. H. (2020). Transformational leadership style, followership, and factors of employees' reactions towards organizational change. *Journal of Asia Business Studies*, 14(2), 181–209. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JABS-03-2018-0083>
- 11) Çiçek, B., & Kılınç, E. (2021). Can transformational leadership eliminate the negativity of technostress? Insights from the logistic industry. *Business & Management Studies: An International Journal*, 9(1), 372–384. <https://doi.org/10.15295/bmij.v9i1.1770>
- 12) De Cuyper, N., Smet, K., & De Witte, H. (2021). I Should Learn to Feel Secure but I Don't Because I Feel Insecure: The Relationship between Qualitative Job Insecurity and Work-Related Learning in the Public Sector. *Review of Public Personnel Administration*, 42(4), 760–785. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734371X211032391>
- 13) De Witte, H., Nawrocka, S., Pasini, M., & Brondino, M. (2023). A Person-Centered Approach to Job Insecurity: Is There a Reciprocal Relationship between the Quantitative and Qualitative Dimensions of Job Insecurity? *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(7). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20075280>
- 14) De Witte, H., Vander Elst, T., & De Cuyper, N. (2015). Job Insecurity, Health and Well-Being (pp. 109–128). https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-017-9798-6_7
- 15) Dinc, M. S., Kuzey, C., & Steta, N. (2018). Nurses' job satisfaction as a mediator of the relationship between organizational commitment components and job performance. *Journal of Workplace Behavioral Health*, 33(2), 75–95. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15555240.2018.1464930>
- 16) Eliyana, A., Ma'arif, S., & Muzakki. (2019a). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment effect in the transformational leadership towards employee performance. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 25(3), 144–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iemeen.2019.05.001>
- 17) Eliyana, A., Ma'arif, S., & Muzakki. (2019b). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment effect in the transformational leadership towards employee performance. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 25(3), 144–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iemeen.2019.05.001>
- 18) Eliyana, A., Ma'arif, S., & Muzakki. (2019c). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment effect in the transformational leadership towards employee performance. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 25(3), 144–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iemeen.2019.05.001>

- 19) Eliyana, A., Ma'arif, S., & Muzakki. (2019d). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment effect in the transformational leadership towards employee performance. *European Research on Management and Business Economics*, 25(3), 144–150. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iedeen.2019.05.001>
- 20) Gaskin, J., Ogbeibu, S., & Lowry, P. B. (2023). Demystifying Prediction in Mediation Research and the Use of Specific Indirect Effects and Indirect Effect Sizes. In H. Latan, Jr. Hair Joseph F., & R. Noonan (Eds.), *Partial Least Squares Path Modeling: Basic Concepts, Methodological Issues and Applications* (pp. 209–228). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-37772-3_8
- 21) Gaye, Ö., & Cavide, B. U. (2019). Performance Management Systems: Task-Contextual Dilemma Owing to the Involvement of the Psychological Contract and Organizational Citizenship Behavior. *European Management Review*, 16(2), 347–362. <https://doi.org/10.1111/emre.12167>
- 22) Gazi, M. A. I., Islam, M. A., Shaturaev, J., & Dhar, B. K. (2022). Effects of Job Satisfaction on Job Performance of Sugar Industrial Workers: Empirical Evidence from Bangladesh. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(21). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142114156>
- 23) Goetz, N., & Wald, A. (2022). Similar but different? The influence of job satisfaction, organizational commitment and person-job fit on individual performance in the continuum between permanent and temporary organizations. *International Journal of Project Management*, 40(3), 251–261. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijproman.2022.03.001>
- 24) Gün, İ., Söyük, S., & Özşari, S. H. (2021). Effects of Job Satisfaction, Affective Commitment, and Organizational Support on Job Performance and Turnover Intention in Healthcare Workers. *Archives of Health Science and Research*, 8(2), 89–95. <https://doi.org/10.5152/ArcHealthSciRes.2021.21044>
- 25) Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M., Sarstedt, M., Danks, N. P., & Ray, S. (2021). An Introduction to Structural Equation Modeling. In J. F. Hair Jr., G. T. M. Hult, C. M. Ringle, M. Sarstedt, N. P. Danks, & S. Ray (Eds.), *Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) Using R: A Workbook* (pp. 1–29). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-80519-7_1
- 26) Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M., & Ringle, C. M. (2019). When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. In *European Business Review* (Vol. 31, Issue 1, pp. 2–24). Emerald Group Publishing Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EBR-11-2018-0203>
- 27) Hallo, L., Nguyen, T., Gorod, A., & Tran, P. (2020). Effectiveness of leadership decision-making in complex systems. *Systems*, 8(1), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.3390/systems8010005>
- 28) Indradewa, R., Lestariani, R. I., Nurhayati Achmad, & Yanuar, T. (2020). The Effect of Transformational Leadership on Affective Commitments with Job Satisfaction and Organizational Culture as An Intervening Variable. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Academic*, 4(6).
- 29) Jiatong, W., Wang, Z., Alam, M., Murad, M., Gul, F., & Gill, S. A. (2022). The Impact of Transformational Leadership on Affective Organizational Commitment and Job Performance: The Mediating Role of Employee Engagement. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.831060>
- 30) Kalia, N., & Bhardwaj, B. (2019). Contextual and Task Performance: Do Demographic and Organizational variables matter? *Rajagiri Management Journal*, 13(2), 30–42. <https://doi.org/10.1108/RAMJ-09-2019-0017>
- 31) Katebi, A., HajiZadeh, M. H., Bordbar, A., & Salehi, A. M. (2022). The Relationship Between “Job Satisfaction” and “Job Performance”: A Meta-analysis. *Global Journal of Flexible Systems Management*, 23(1), 21–42. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40171-021-00280-y>
- 32) Kaur Bagga, S., Gera, S., & Haque, S. N. (2023). The mediating role of organizational culture: Transformational leadership and change management in virtual teams. *Asia Pacific Management Review*, 28(2), 120–131. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2022.07.003>

- 33) Kleszczewska, D., Mazur, J., & Siedlecka, J. (2019). Family, school and neighborhood factors moderating the relationship between physical activity and some aspects of mental health in adolescents. In *International Journal of Occupational Medicine and Environmental Health* (Vol. 32, Issue 4, pp. 423–439). Nofer Institute of Occupational Medicine. <https://doi.org/10.13075/ijomeh.1896.01389>
- 34) Koen, J., Low, J. T. H., & Van Vianen, A. (2020). Job preservation efforts: when does job insecurity prompt performance? *Career Development International*, 25(3), 287–305. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CDI-04-2018-0099>
- 35) Koo, B., Yu, J., Chua, B.-L., Lee, S., & Han, H. (2020). Relationships among Emotional and Material Rewards, Job Satisfaction, Burnout, Affective Commitment, Job Performance, and Turnover Intention in the Hotel Industry. *Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality & Tourism*, 21(4), 371–401. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1528008X.2019.1663572>
- 36) Koopmans, L., Bernaards, C. M., Hildebrandt, V. H., van Buuren, S., van der Beek, A. J., & de Vet, H. C. W. (2014). Improving the Individual Work Performance Questionnaire using Rasch analysis. *Journal of Applied Measurement*, 15(2), 160–175. <https://doi.org/10.1136/oemed-2013-101717.51>
- 37) Kumar, S., & Bhandarker, A. (2021). Transformational leadership in AICTE: lessons for organizational excellence. *Emerald Emerging Markets Case Studies*, 11(3). <https://doi.org/10.1108/EEMCS-08-2020-0299>
- 38) Kustiawan, U., Marpaung, P., Lestari, U. D., & Andiyana, E. (2022). The Effect of Affective Organizational Commitment, Job Satisfaction, and Employee Engagement on Job Happiness and Job Performance on Manufacturing Company in Indonesia. *WSEAS Transactions on Business and Economics*, 19. <https://doi.org/10.37394/23207.2022.19.52>
- 39) Lachowicz, M. J., Preacher, K. J., & Kelley, K. (2018). A novel measure of effect size for mediation analysis. *Psychological Methods*, 23(2), 244–261. <https://doi.org/10.1037/met0000165>
- 40) Langerak, J. B., Koen, J., & van Hooft, E. A. J. (2022). How to minimize job insecurity: The role of proactive and reactive coping over time. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 136, 103729. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jvb.2022.103729>
- 41) Langster, H. J., & Cutrer, S. (2021). A scoping review of the impact of downsizing on survivors. In *Journal of Nursing Administration* (Vol. 51, Issue 6). Lippincott Williams and Wilkins. <https://doi.org/10.1097/NNA.0000000000001022>
- 42) Lee, C. C., Yeh, W. C., Yu, Z., & Lin, X. C. (2023). The relationships between leader emotional intelligence, transformational leadership, and transactional leadership and job performance: A mediator model of trust. *Heliyon*, 9(8). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e18007>
- 43) Lee, S., Hong, S., & Lee, B. G. (2023). Is There a Right Way to Lay Off Employees in Times of Crisis?: The Role of Organizational Justice in the Case of Airbnb. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 15(5). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su15054690>
- 44) Llosa, J. A., Agulló-Tomás, E., Menéndez-Espina, S., Heleno, C. T., & de Olivera Borges, L. (2023). Cross-cultural adaptation of the Job Insecurity Scale (JIS) in Brazil and cross-national analysis of Job Insecurity effects in Brazil and Spain. *BMC Psychology*, 11(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-023-01156-9>
- 45) Luthans, F., Luthans, B. C., & Luthans, K. W. (2021). *Organizational Behavior: An Evidence-Based Approach* (14th ed.). Information Age Publishing, Inc.
- 46) Luu, D. T., & Phan, H. Van. (2020). The Effects of Transformational Leadership and Job Satisfaction on Commitment to Organisational Change: A Three-Component Model Extension Approach. *The South East Asian Journal of Management*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.21002/seam.v14i1.11585>
- 47) Lyubykh, Z., Gulseren, D., Turner, N., Barling, J., & Seifert, M. (2022). Shared transformational leadership and safety behaviours of employees, leaders, and teams: A multilevel investigation. *Journal of Occupational and Organizational Psychology*, 95(2), 431–458. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joop.12381>

- 48) Manzoor, F., Wei, L., Nurunnabi, M., Subhan, Q. A., Shah, S. H. A., & Fallatah, S. (2019). The Impact of Transformational Leadership on Job Performance and CSR as Mediator in SMEs. Sustainability. <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:113403978>
- 49) Memon, M. A., Ting, H., Cheah, J. H., Thurasamy, R., Chuah, F., & Cham, T. H. (2020). Sample size for survey research: Review and recommendations. *Journal of Applied Structural Equation Modeling*, 4(2), i–xx. [https://doi.org/10.47263/jasem.4\(2\)01](https://doi.org/10.47263/jasem.4(2)01)
- 50) Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (1991). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *Human Resource Management Review*, 1(1), 61–89. [https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/1053-4822\(91\)90011-Z](https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/1053-4822(91)90011-Z)
- 51) Moin, M. F., Omar, M. K., Wei, F., Rasheed, M. I., & Hameed, Z. (2021). Green HRM and psychological safety: how transformational leadership drives follower's job satisfaction. *Current Issues in Tourism*, 24(16), 2269–2277. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13683500.2020.1829569>
- 52) Nauman, S., Bhatti, S., Jalil, F., & Bint E Riaz, M. (2021). How training at work influences employees' job satisfaction: roles of affective commitment and job performance. *International Journal of Training Research*, 19(1), 61–76. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14480220.2020.1864444>
- 53) Nielsen, M. B., Hetland, J., Harris, A., Notelaers, G., Gjerstad, J., & Einarsen, S. V. (2022). The impact of follower leadership position on transformational leadership as moderator of the association between work-related ambiguity and job satisfaction. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.970887>
- 54) Nugroho, S. H., & Pudiastuti, E. T. (2021). Analysis of Organizational Performance through Transformational Leadership and Organizational Culture. *International Journal of ASPRO*, 12(1).
- 55) O', C., Iii, R., & Chatman, J. (1986). Organizational Commitment and Psychological Attachment: The Effects of Compliance, Identification, and Internalization on Prosocial Behavior. In *Journal of Applied Psychology* (Vol. 71, Issue 3).
- 56) Park, J., Han, S. J., Kim, J., & Kim, W. (2022). Structural relationships among transformational leadership, affective organizational commitment, and job performance: the mediating role of employee engagement. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 46(9), 920–936. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJTD-10-2020-0149>
- 57) Perneger, T. V., Courvoisier, D. S., Hudelson, P. M., & Gayet-Ageron, A. (2015). Sample size for pre-tests of questionnaires. *Quality of Life Research*, 24(1), 147–151. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11136-014-0752-2>
- 58) Qian, S., Yuan, Q., Niu, W., & Liu, Z. (2022). Is job insecurity always bad? The moderating role of job embeddedness in the relationship between job insecurity and job performance. *Journal of Management & Organization*, 28(5), 956–972. <https://doi.org/DOI: 10.1017/jmo.2018.77>
- 59) Riania, P. A., & Nisa, P. C. (2022). Pengaruh Job Insecurity Terhadap Turnover Intention yang dimediasi Job Satisfaction, Affective Organizational Commitment, dan Work Engagement Karyawan Pabrik yang Sudah Menikah. *E-Mabis: Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Dan Bisnis*, 23(2). <https://doi.org/10.29103/e-mabis.v23i2.858>
- 60) Robbins, & Judge, T. (2022). *Organizational Behavior, Updated Global Edition (18th ed.)*. Pearson Higher Ed.
- 61) Shao, H., Fu, H., Ge, Y., Jia, W., Li, Z., & Wang, J. (2022). Moderating Effects of Transformational Leadership, Affective Commitment, Job Performance, and Job Insecurity. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.847147>
- 62) Shoss, M., Su, S., Schlotzhauer, A., & Carusone, N. (2020, September 26). *Job Insecurity Harms Both Employees and Employers*. Harvard Business School.
- 63) Spector, P. (2022). *Job Satisfaction from Assessment to Intervention (1st ed.)*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/DOI: 10.4324/9781003250616>
- 64) Sürücü, L., Maslakçı, A., & Sesen, H. (2022). Transformational leadership, job performance, self-efficacy, and leader support: testing a moderated mediation model. *Baltic Journal of Management*, 17(4), 467–483. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BJM-08-2021-0306>

- 65) Syafitri, J. T., Laura, S., & Rahmi, F. (2022). The Relationship Of Job Insecurity, Affective Commitment, And Job Performance. *Mantik Journal*, 6(1), 10–17.
- 66) Taduvana, S., Msosa, S. K., & Chikukwa, T. (2022). Job insecurity, job satisfaction and organisational commitment in turbulent economic times at a textile and clothing manufacturing company. *Quality - Access to Success*, 23(186), 23–29. <https://doi.org/10.47750/QAS/23.186.04>
- 67) Tjahjono, H. K., Kurnia, M., Rahayu, P., Dirgantara Putra, A., & Putra, A. D. (2020). The Mediating Role of Affective Commitment on The Effect of Perceived Organizational Support and Procedural Justice on Job Performance of Civil Servant *Journal of Leadership in Organizations*. In *Journal of Leadership in Organizations* (Vol. 2, Issue 2).
- 68) Torlak, N. G., & Kuzey, C. (2019). Leadership, job satisfaction and performance links in private education institutes of Pakistan. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 68(2), 276–295. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-05-2018-0182>
- 69) van Vuuren, T., de Jong, J. P., & Smulders, P. G. W. (2019). The association between subjective job insecurity and job performance across different employment groups. *Career Development International*, 25(3), 229–246. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1108/CDI-05-2018-0155>
- 70) Wayoi, D. S., Margana, M., Prasajo, L. D., & Habibi, A. (2021). Dataset on Islamic school teachers' organizational commitment as factors affecting job satisfaction and job performance. *Data in Brief*, 37, 107181. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dib.2021.107181>
- 71) Weiss, D. J., Dawis, R. V, & England, G. W. (1967). Manual for the Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire. *Minnesota Studies in Vocational Rehabilitation*, 22, 120.
- 72) Zeng, N., Liu, Y., Gong, P., Hertogh, M., & König, M. (2021). Do right PLS and do PLS right: A critical review of the application of PLS-SEM in construction management research. *Frontiers of Engineering Management*, 8(3), 356–369. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42524-021-0153-5>